

Housing financialisation as a tool of managing dependent integration - the case of Hungary between 2008 and 2024

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Abstract

In this paper, we analyse how housing policy and financial cycles interact, through the case study of Hungary in the period between 2008 and 2024. The main contribution of the paper is twofold: first, to highlight how housing financialization serves the political and economic interests of an authoritarian-leaning political regime, in the context of the dependent economic integration of the country. We underline how housing, as well as the industries connected to it are specifically important for the electoral and economic base of the Hungarian government. Second, the paper employs a cyclical analysis, following how homeownership-based housing financialisation, which is characteristic of the Central and Eastern European region, changes its appearance but not its fundamental nature through various financial cycles.

Hungary is an interesting case study since it was considered to take unorthodox paths in terms of economic policy, especially in the years following the 2008 crisis. While the intertwined nature of financial capitalism and new authoritarian regimes has been noted in the literature, the specific role of housing in this connection is often overlooked. In the paper we give an overview of three phases of housing financialisation in Hungary: from 2008 to 2015, from 2015 to 2022 and from 2022 onwards.

Keywords

Financialisation,
housing, dependent
integration, Hungary

Introduction

This paper aims to understand the recent, post-2008, trends of housing financialisation in Hungary. We take the case of Hungary as a framework for understanding how the state actions translate broader changes in financial cycles, and the specific role that housing policy and housing finance can play in this connection. More specifically, we analyse how international financial subordination (Alami et. al 2021) or financialized dependence (Reis and Antunas de Oliveira 2021) is connected to local policy shifts on the Hungarian housing market – and vice-versa, how shifts on the housing market are instruments of the Hungarian

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state and its economic actors in mitigating the economically and financially dependent, or subordinate position of the country. Thus, our aim is to bring current international literature on the topic of financial subordination into conversation with literature on housing financialization and housing policy in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), and specifically in Hungary. We contribute to the existing literature in two main ways. First, by focusing specifically on the case of housing within the broader discussions of financialization and financial subordination in the region and in Hungary. Second, by employing a cyclical approach and showing how the homeownership-based form of housing financialization which is characteristic of the country (and of the CEE region more broadly) changes its appearance, but not its fundamental nature across various economic and financial cycles.

The case of Hungary is illustrative because of the extremity of processes relating to housing financialisation both before and after the 2008 financial crisis. Before 2008, Hungary was a schoolbook example of internationally directly dependent housing financialisation, with a very high share of mortgages denominated in foreign currencies and a rapidly increasing mortgage penetration among households. After the crisis, from 2010 onwards the new conservative government implemented a number of measures severing the international dependency of housing finance. A series of policies were introduced aiming to decouple housing finance in Hungary from direct international dependency. This mainly happened through the downscaling of household debt denominated in foreign currencies, finally converting most of the remaining debt to Hungarian Forints. A shift in bank ownership also happened in this period, from foreign to domestic dominance.

In a next phase, from 2015 onwards, a new, domestic regime of housing financialization was rolled out. Between 2015 and 2022, a self-reinforcing, synergetic system of housing financialisation was built up in Hungary which served the interests of a government and local elite navigating the dependent economic position of the country. During this period, public debt was restructured towards domestic (and individual) creditors, and private debt massively expanded with the support of different programs subsidised by the government, and as a consequence of generally low interest rates. This all happened in the broader context of a period of economic expansion. Some measures of this regime – such as subsidised loans connected to the number of children a family has – have also been taken over by other governments in the CEE region. This system of housing financialization supported access to homeownership for middle class families, and also strengthened specific, preferential companies of the construction and financial industries.

This specific structure of housing financialization started to waver and show its flaws in 2022, when interest rates and inflation hiked. This latest period will most likely bring a new,

reorganized form of housing financialisation. This includes a strong reduction of available subsidies to homeownership, and a likely increase of investor-buyers (potentially also of institutional investors) on the Hungarian housing market. There is also an increasing number of foreign buyers on the Hungarian housing market, whose share increased by over 30% from 2021 to 2022 (Futó 2023). One of the reasons for this can be the repeated waves of devaluation of the Hungarian Forint (speeding up again since 2020), which makes the Hungarian housing market more affordable to European investors. These tendencies together signal the returning of a more internationally dependent form of housing financialization. Non-financialized housing forms could also benefit from this crisis period and seek to expand, but the dominant political and economic interests do not serve this – thus, if it happens, it will be as a result of counter-hegemonic interventions.

In the paper, we analyse the above three phases of shifting housing financialisation in Hungary: from 2008 to 2015, from 2015 to 2022, and from 2022 onwards. The Hungarian case is interesting to understand also in international comparison, because it sheds light on the potential strategies of other countries in similar positions of financial subordination and dependent economies. These different cycles of housing financialisation can be seen as a shifting pattern of managing various factors connected to the housing market: the exchange rate between the Hungarian Forint and the Euro, the cost of borrowing and the costs of construction, as well as social pressures and electoral cycles. The housing market, as well as the industries connected to it (such as the construction and financial industries) have become essential for the ruling Fidesz-led government in creating new capital accumulations. Thus, while the main beneficiaries of the pre-2008 regime of housing financialisation were international banking groups and foreign construction companies, after 2008 this was reshuffled. With the shift in bank ownership and the new system of public subsidies for purchasing housing (introduced in 2015), domestic financial institutions became the beneficiaries of housing finance, while domestic construction companies, several with connections to the governing party, became the main providers of new-built housing. Thus, housing finance has become an important part of the rentier bargain that supports the government in maintaining its political power. Common to the different periods is that housing provision has not been decoupled from the financial logic in Hungary. The essential nature of the policy tools related to housing are the same throughout the discussed phases, aiming to support the middle classes' access to homeownership. It is merely the specific form of housing financialisation; its intermediaries and beneficiaries, which have changed. These shifts can be seen as strategies of the state in a semi-peripheral global position to manage processes of financialisation to the economic and political benefit of certain interest groups, which pursue their interests through the state in different ways.

The paper builds on publicly available data. The main contribution of the paper is to demonstrate, through the specific case of Hungary, how housing policy can become one of the important channels for managing shifts in financial cycles, in a country which is in a position of financial subordination on the international scene.

Linking “domestic” processes of housing financialisation to international economic dependency

We take the conceptual approach of understanding local (national-scale) processes of housing financialisation in their connection to global processes and to the position of Hungary within the global economy and financial system. In doing so, we draw on the work of Alami et al. (2022) on international financial subordination (IFS), Fernandez and Aalbers (2020) on housing financialisation in the Global South, Bonizzi et al. (2022) on financialised capitalism and financial subordination, Becker et al. (2015) on their analysis of European-scale dependencies, and on Karas’s (2021) detailed analysis of financialisation in Hungary after the 2008 crisis. Common to these bodies of work is that they understand domestic economic processes inherently connected to unequal international relations and global economic hierarchies. In these unequal relations, finance plays a crucial role in contemporary capitalism, and is thus set at the centre of the analysis. As noted by Alami et al. (2022), Bonizzi et al. (2022) and others, finance also plays a crucial role in the transfer of value from subordinated economies to core economies. This chimes with the “financial chain” approach (Sokol, 2017; Sokol and Pataccini, 2020; see below). At the same time, the above-mentioned studies also scrutinize the role the peripheral or subordinated state can play in steering financialisation (or generally, financial relations) according to its political and economic interests.

We put the above literature in conversation with insights on housing policy and housing financialisation. While most literature on international dependent relations had traditionally focused on relations of production, with the more recent body of literature outlined above, which focuses on finance, it becomes easier to put housing at the centre of the analysis. One of the key elements in this relation is debt. Housing debt enables households to become one of the “drivers” of debt-fuelled growth, thus increasing the stock of household debt – in which housing-related debt represents the largest volume – corresponds to the interests of many different actors.

Contrary to previous understandings of international dependent relations, recent studies suggest that export-led growth and financialisation are not contradictory to each other in (semi-)peripheral countries (Bonizzi et al. 2022, Gerócs 2021). The conventional view in the

domains of dependency theory was that countries which are in a globally dependent position usually rely on exports to finance their need for international currency, while debt-fuelled asset price growth was “traditionally” seen as the privilege of core countries. However, it appears that the dichotomy between an export-led growth regime and a (debt-financed) consumption-led growth regime is no longer useful in the post-2008 environment (Kohler and Stockhammer 2022). Rather, the above can be seen as different “optimization” strategies during different periods of time for governments and economic elites of countries in a dependent position (Reis and Antunas de Oliveira 2021). Indeed, the most recent empirical evidence suggests that we witness a mixing of these strategies and that economically dependent countries too have started producing debt-fuelled asset prices increases. Karas (2021) also cites a number of cases of non-core economies (such as Turkey or Russia), where these asset price booms are fuelled by state-led financialisation – underlining that this is indeed a part of the state’s broader economic strategy as well.

In this context, it is salutary to remember that Central and Eastern European economies (including Hungary) were described as “dependent market economies” (Nölke and Vliegthart, 2009) where both production and finance are in the hands of foreign (mostly Western European) corporate groups. This dependence on Western capital is a source of both economic strength and economic vulnerability. The latter became painfully evident through the global financial crisis of 2008. In post-2008-crisis Hungary, the Fidesz government (in power since 2010) continued the FDI-based, export orientated “dependent production”, but chose to radically tackle the “dependent finance” (Ban and Bohle, 2021). One of the key features of this strategy was to dramatically reduce the foreign ownership of financial institutions and to boost the domestic control of the banking sector. However, rather than achieving “definancialisation” (as implied by Ban and Bohle, 2021), it may be more accurate to describe the process as domestically-orchestrated state-led financialisation. We want to draw attention to the fact that housing-related debt played an important role in this process, while also being one of the more important forms of dependent finance during the pre-2008 period.

If we take the analysis of these instances of state-led financialisation further, we can see that in many cases, financialisation processes can actually serve the economic and political interests of illiberal regimes very well. Besides the contemporary cases of Hungary (Gerócs 2021), Turkey, Russia or China (Karas 2021), the historical example of the connection between the 1931 banking crisis and the rise of Hitler has also been demonstrated (Doerr et al. 2021). In Central and Eastern Europe, such a case is perhaps more surprising, given the small size of the economies in the region. In the case of Hungary, different authors have labelled this “nationalised” form of financial capitalism in different ways. Geva (2021) uses the term of

“ordonationalism”, emphasizing how the conservative regime in power in Hungary since 2010 emerged from the 2008 crisis. However, Geva emphasizes that in economic terms, this regime is just as neoliberal as the previous ones, only through the enhancement of domestic capitalist markets. Sebők (2019) describes how the different strategies of financial capitalism in Hungary were the result of how different elite fractions and their ideologies competed with each other. He also uses the term “financial nationalism” to frame the regime that emerged after 2010. Likewise – and following Johnson and Barnes (2015) – the term “financial nationalism” is used also by Ban and Bohle (2021) in connection to Hungary. “Financial nationalism” could be described as “an economic strategy that seeks to increase the national room for manoeuvre in financial matters, and to selectively reward economic insiders” (Ban and Bohle, 2021, p. 878). Again, it is worth adding that financial nationalism does not necessarily mean financial repression or the end of financialisation. This framework can be well adapted to the case of housing financialisation in Hungary, where the period between 2015 and 2022 can be seen as an illustrative example of how “financial nationalism” plays out in practice.

What the above authors frame as “dependent finance” and “financial nationalism”, Karas (2021) describes as the multi-dimensionality of financialisation in Hungary after the 2008 crisis. He identifies different domains (e.g. housing, retail banking) and dimensions of financialisation, in which the processes that have recently unfolded are not homogenous. The broader framework of the analysis is how the Hungarian state manages external financial relations. Karas identifies a “financial vertical”, in which different reactive and proactive channels were activated, influencing how financialisation rolls out in different domains. The different aspects and instruments of the reactive channel (such as reducing forex denominated debt and foreign holding of debt) have served to weaken financialisation, while aspects of the proactive channel (such as boosting the construction sector or providing subsidised loans for homeownership) have deepened financialisation (Karas 2021, p.6). This analysis can also be linked to the claim of Fernandez and Aalbers that “...empirically speaking, financialisation in some domains may be happening alongside nonfinancialisation in other domains” (Fernandez and Aalbers, 2020, p.681).

The idea of the reactive and proactive channels of the financial vertical can also be related to the concept of “financial chains” (Sokol, 2017). Financial chains can be understood both as “channels of value transfer (between people and places) and as social relations that shape socio-economic processes and attendant economic geographies” (Sokol, 2017, p. 683). The global financial crisis of 2008 and more recently the Covid-induced crisis of 2020, have shaken financial chains and almost brought down the entire financial system. The financial collapse has only been prevented through state interventions, including massive interventions of

central banks (Sokol and Pataccini, 2020; Sokol, 2022). It is useful to note that these interventions have been happening in the context of increasing “state capitalist” tendencies around the world (Alami and Dixon, 2020; Alami and Dixon, 2021). Unconventional monetary policies by central banks can be seen as one of the features of “state capitalism” (Sokol, 2022). The role of the state and of the central bank is also pertinent in the Hungarian case. Indeed, as Ban and Bohle (2021) note, radical changes that the Hungarian government introduced in the 2010s would not be possible without a supporting muscle of the Hungarian central bank. The fact that Hungary is not part of the Eurozone gave the Hungarian state and its central bank the flexibility needed to intervene. The way in which financial chains have been remodelled in Hungary in different periods will be analysed in the subsequent sections relating to the financialisation of housing.

In an ambitious recent proposal for a research agenda on what they call international financial subordination (IFS), Alami et al. (2021) argue (following Fernandez and Aalbers, 2020 and others) that housing finance and patterns of urban growth in financially subordinated countries can be linked to financial flows from advanced economies (and this has been an important feature in pre-crisis Hungary), and also specifically mention the “re-nationalisation” of financial systems as one of the strategies a state can employ in a position of financial subordination. Some of these dimensions can thus be usefully applied to the empirical evidence of housing financialisation and housing finance in Hungary, allowing us to go into the details of how housing financialisation unfolds in a variegated way.

Besides the above theoretical frameworks, we will also heavily draw on recent research which is more directly concerned with financialisation in Hungary (Karas 2021, Ban and Bohle 2021), with housing financialisation in dependent positions (Vincze 2023, Mikus and Rodik 2021a, Fernandez and Aalbers 2020), and with financial subordination in Eastern Europe (Mikus 2019, Pataccini 2021).

Variegated forms of housing financialisation in Hungary between 2008 and 2024

In the two decades between 2004 and 2024, housing financialisation has changed its appearance several times in Hungary, in accordance with shifting financial cycles and shifting policy measures. Our argument is that in spite of this, the fundamental nature of housing financialisation in Hungary has not changed, and forms of housing provision which would be less dominated by the financial logic have not been able to emerge on a larger scale. While the pre-2008 period has been extensively covered in the literature (for example see Hegedüs and

Somogyi 2016 or Gagyí 2023), we analyse the shifting manifestations of housing financialisation across three periods after 2008: 2008-2015, 2015-2022, and 2022 onwards.

In our analysis of the Hungarian housing market, we will focus on these distinct phases and the critical turning points (2008, 2015 and 2022), using them as a means of illustrating how housing financialisation is transformed under different economic circumstances within a semi-peripheral country. We will also highlight the spatial, geographical consequences of these different regimes of housing financialisation. Our analysis will give special attention to the period between 2015 and 2022, aiming to elucidate how housing financialisation has contributed to the stabilization of the Fidesz government's power in Hungary.

1) Post-2008 crisis management

The 2008 crisis was an important turning point in how housing financialisation unfolds in Hungary. Before, starting from 2004, there was a quick build-up of household loans denominated in foreign currencies (forex loans). Once the financial crisis hit, this large stock of forex loans made Hungary one of the obvious cases for understanding the dramatic implications of direct external financial dependency in the field of housing finance (Florea, Gagyí and Jacobsson 2022). In this period, a series of measures aiming to manage the so-called forex crisis were introduced. These measures were discussed in detail by various authors (see eg. Hegedüs and Somogyi 2016, Czirfusz and Jelinek 2021). Thus, in this article we only highlight some key features of this phase.

The two main directions of interventions in the field of housing finance were the following:

(i) Managing the social consequences of debt default. This mainly meant different interventions that allowed debtors to repay or refinance loans with favourable conditions, and ultimately a possibility to convert forex loans to loans denominated in the Hungarian currency Forint. The majority of these measures supported better-off debtors to a higher extent, while many lower income debtors continued to face difficulties of payment or foreclosure.

(ii) Reducing external (foreign) dependency in housing finance. This was mainly achieved through banning loans denominated in foreign currencies (unless the debtor had an income in the same foreign currency), and through supporting an increasing share of domestic ownership in banks.

A number of other – mainly macroeconomic – measures implemented in this period are discussed in the paper of Karas (2021). During this phase, actors within the state were also shifting. The function of financial market supervision and regulation was taken from an

independent agency (Hungarian Financial Supervisory Authority) and put within the Hungarian National Bank (Magyar Nemzeti Bank), the central bank of Hungary.

Contrary to what the classical IFS / dependency school would expect, in this phase the Hungarian government largely discontinued across-the-board de-risking for foreign investors and foreign financial institutions. While de-risking and subsidies supporting foreign market actors continued and even increased in some sectors of the economy; most notably in the automotive industry; legal frameworks and financially supportive measures were introduced to the benefit of domestic economic actors in other sectors, most notably in the real estate and financial industries. As a result, direct foreign dependency and capital outflows were reduced specifically in the field of housing finance through the measures described above. However, this happened together with a repositioning of dominant domestic economic actors, preparing – as we will see in the following section – the scene for a new form of housing financialisation, which then generated a domestic asset price bubble.

These interventions aiming to reduce household indebtedness in foreign currencies (and decreasing dependence on foreign finance in the field of housing and real estate more generally) led some authors (e.g. Ban and Bohle 2021) to claim that processes of housing de-financialisation have been happening in Hungary after 2008. However, an alternative interpretation is that these measures merely meant the repression of the financial logic in some specific fields and forms of housing finance, while preparing the ground for the unfolding of a new form of domestically based housing financialisation.

2) The housing market boom between 2015 and 2022

2015 brought a new turning point in housing financialisation in Hungary, since this year marks the beginning of a new housing market boom in the country. This phase of housing market upswing introduced a system of “national” housing financialisation – although it happened in the more general context of low interest rates and intensifying housing market investments across Europe. This phase of housing finance was also characterized by increasing inequalities and socio-spatial unevenness on the housing market, intensified by pro-cyclical government interventions. We argue that this period is one of “national” housing financialisation, since it strongly builds on domestic economic actors and it was also built up in a way to support the political power of the government. Domestically owned banks and real estate developers became the main beneficiaries of this regime of housing financialisation, besides middle class households who gained assets through homeownership.

In practical terms, a new set of subsidies was rolled out following 2015. Although this set of housing subsidies became very important in the political communication of the Fidesz government, presenting it as their own innovation, it was actually, in its essence, very similar to the housing subsidy that existed before, since the early 1970s until 2009 (Czirfusz and Jelinek 2021). The central element is a subsidy for families, the amount of which depends on the number of children they have. The grant is available for building or purchasing property for their own residential purposes. It has, however, been demonstrated that the current phase of subsidies is more unequal than previous forms; being more biased towards financially better-off families (Czirfusz and Jelinek 2021). These subsidies are available through banks, which is a very pragmatic demonstration of how housing provision has been financialized in Hungary.

Since 2015, the main housing-related subsidy is called the "Home Creation Subsidy for Families" (in Hungarian: Családok Otthonteremtési Kedvezménye or CSOK). In its form available until the end of 2023, it was accessible to couples and single parents depending on the number of children they had. Individuals who were less than 40 years old could also access the subsidy based on children they promised to have in the future. A subsidised mortgage loan (with a fixed interest of 3%) could also be accessed by those recipients who had (or promised to have) at least 2 children.

Another type of subsidised home loan was for renovation - this involved smaller sums and could be accessed by couples or single parents with at least one child. This loan acted as a bridge loan for a post-financed grant ("Home Renovation Subsidy") available for renovation with the same conditions attached (i.e. at least one child).

A third type of subsidised mortgage loan was the "Green Home Loan", which could be used for purchasing newly built housing (or building new housing) with a very high (BB or higher) energy performance. This subsidised loan was only available between October 2021 and May 2022, but during this period was extremely popular among high income people buying housing, and in the second quarter of 2022, accounted for 33% of all newly issued housing loans, and 85% of loans issued for a newly constructed property (MNB 2022a).

A fourth type of subsidised loan (not mortgage) was the "Baby Expecting Loan", which was a free-purpose consumer loan, but many families used it for housing purposes. This was a zero-interest loan of maximum cc 25.000 euros, available to married couples, which they needed to apply for before the baby was born. If the baby was born, the loan became interest free, and after the birth of subsequent children, the loan capital was partially or entirely transformed into a grant. This loan was extremely popular in the years following its

introduction in 2019, and in June 2022 accounted for 18% of the total outstanding loan volume among households (MNB 2022a).

These subsidies and subsidised loans were rolled out in a period of historically low interest rates, which boosted new lending for housing purposes independently from subsidies. However, it contributed to a process of state-led financialisation that housing-related support was almost exclusively available to Hungarian households through various publicly subsidised financial products. This was further pushed by the Hungarian central bank's policy over the past years to increase lending. Even in early March 2022 amid rising interest rates, the governor of the central bank appraised their debt-based crisis management strategy during the two years of Covid (Matolcsy 2022). This debt-based strategy was, on the one hand, a quasi quantitative easing instrument introduced by the Magyar Nemzeti Bank during the Covid-19 pandemic, and on the other hand, the sustained system of subsidised household loans. As a result of the combination of these factors, record volumes of new housing-purpose lending (which got to higher levels than pre-2008) were recorded, driving an asset price bubble. Thus, Hungary experienced the most dramatic house price increase (+128% nationally and +134% in Budapest) among all EU countries between 2015 and 2021 (EMF 2022).

A further aspect of state-led financialization in this period was the introduction of a framework for domestic individuals to buy state bonds at favourable conditions. This scheme became very popular, and new series of state bonds continue to be issued until today (early 2024). This mechanism also contributed to the synergetic system of strengthening the electoral base (only financially better off citizens had resources to channel into this very favourable savings scheme), while also having the benefit, from the perspective of the state, to decrease foreign debt dependency. After the Covid-induced crisis, and during the inflationary period starting in 2022, the Hungarian state continued to issue state bonds available to the public at ever higher interest rates as part of their debt-based crisis management strategy.

The cycle between 2015 and 2022 was, altogether, characterised by a self-reinforcing regime of housing financialisation in Hungary, based on a quickly expanding stock of new housing loans, boosted by a system of state subsidies coupled by subsidised mortgages for childbearing families. Beside families, real estate developers also benefited from the stream of new finance available on the housing markets, and the subsidies quickly translated into house price increases. House prices increased in Hungary during this period at the fastest pace within the European Union. Even though house price increases were strongly diversified geographically, by the end of the cycle (between 2020 and 2022), house prices in secondary cities were increasing even faster than in the capital city of Budapest (MNB 2023).

These factors supported a system of national financialisation on the level of the voter base of the government, of domestic companies in the real estate industry, and of nationalized and domestically owned financial institutions. The voter base element of the system manifested itself through continued electoral successes of the Fidesz government in the intervening period. In all elections since 2010 (thus 2010, 2014, 2018 and 2022) Fidesz acquired 67 or 68% of all parliamentary mandates thus ensuring super-majority in the parliament. This concentration of power has had severe political, social and economic consequences in Hungary since 2010, leading to strengthening authoritarianism and economic clientelism. Beyond its political benefits, this system of housing financialisation could solidify the positions of domestic capital in specific strategic economic sectors. However, due to its oligopolistic nature (especially in the field of construction materials and real estate development) it also led to drastic (well above EU average) increases in construction prices, which also contributed to the house price increases - which were already fuelled by the credit boom.

In 2022, this synergetic system of housing finance was shaken by different forms of economic turmoil. Although the government intervened in a regulatory way to prevent a quickly escalating crisis on the housing market; corporate actors have already halted their housing market activities, and important shifts in how finance is channelled into housing can be expected.

3) Unfolding economic turmoil and its consequences for the Hungarian housing market from 2022 onwards

In Hungary, the economic and energy crisis started to unfold very rapidly in the spring of 2022. In 2022 and 2023, inflation rate was among the highest in EU countries, being 14,6% in 2022 and 17% in 2023, but moving around 25% during spring 2023.¹ Market-based gas prices have increased 7-fold, and electricity prices 3-fold when the state subsidy for these utilities was restricted over the summer of 2022. The value of the Hungarian currency, the Forint dropped significantly compared to the Euro. While at the beginning of 2022 the exchange rate was 368 Forints to one Euro, in mid-October 2022 it went up to 430 Forints to one Euro. Later on, this stabilized somewhat, but average exchange rates were still around 375-385 HUF to 1 euro throughout 2023, with a systematic tendency of devaluation restarting towards the end of the year. This systematic currency devaluation also affects the level of inflation in the country. Inflation and currency devaluation were aggravated by the lack of political agreement between the Hungarian government and the European Commission on issues of transparency and human rights, which resulted in the blockage of resources from the Recovery and Resilience Fund, and also in a lack of agreement on Cohesion Policy funds for the 2021-2027

¹ See: <https://tradingeconomics.com/hungary/inflation-cpi>

period. An agreement was eventually reached in December 2022, which led to a temporary strengthening of the Forint, but international trust is still not entirely established, and the usage of funds is connected to the implementation of certain new institutions and guarantees by the Hungarian government. Hoping to curb inflation and currency devaluation, the central bank started raising base interest rates at the beginning of 2022. Between September 2022 and October 2023, the base interest rate in Hungary was at 13% - which was extremely high (for an extensive period) compared to the very slowly raised Eurozone base interest rate (which was still 1,5% in Autumn 2022, and was raised to 3,25-4% in May 2023). In October 2023, a very slow reduction of the base interest rate was started, only to reach 7,75% by April 2024.

This broader context has significant implications for the housing market and for housing finance. On the one hand, existing loans that had a variable interest rate, or a fixed interest rate only for a limited period of time will be experiencing severe interest rate hikes. The government has managed this temporarily by introducing a freeze on interest rate levels of existing loans (at the level of interest rates in October 2021). This has been prolonged several times, and is currently in effect until the end of June 2024. Independently from this regulation, interest rates of newly issued household loans have not entirely followed the hikes of the base interest rate. This means that banks are currently (in late 2023/early 2024) still often lending to households on a negative margin. Such a decision is due to several factors, such as competition between banks, the hope of banks of increasing their market share during this turbulent period, and efforts to sustain their internal human capacities working on household lending (Pósfai et al 2022). Nevertheless, household lending has drastically decreased since the hikes in interest rates.

On the other hand, inflation and general economic recession – and before that, the Covid-19 pandemic and its economic consequences – have taken a toll on the financial situation of households. Financial institutions expect that existing debtors might experience financial difficulties due to the increasing costs of living. Thus, banks are counting on a deteriorating loan portfolio in the coming period (MNB 2022a). Since the end of 2021, short term delays of payment (that is, up to 90 days and from 90 days to 1 year) have steadily been on a higher level than in preceding years. However, this steadily higher level does not seem to further deteriorate, and represents around 1,5% of the total loan stock, with a further 0,8% of long-term, over 1 year delays (MNB 2024). During the Covid-19 pandemic, the government introduced a loan repayment moratorium, which was in place between March 2020 and December 2022. This was a response to the immediate difficulties of payment, but since interest accumulated during the moratorium period, debtors eventually ended up with more

debt as a result. Nevertheless, this was a mechanism that staved off the immediate visibility of the effects of the currently unfolding crisis.

As part of the Hungarian government's pro-cyclical intervention strategy, when crisis signs start to show, they usually also cut housing subsidies. This was also the case during this period. From 2023 onwards, the pool of households who can access various subsidies was strongly restricted. This mainly affected the "Home Creation Subsidy for Families", where the subsidy element is only accessible in villages from 2024 onwards. However, the subsidised loan element was broadened, increasing maximum loan amounts, but making access criteria stricter. The "Baby Expecting Loan" underwent similar changes – although the subsidised maximum loan amount was slightly increased, access was limited to women under 30 years of age. These changes underline the financializing tendency of housing policy in Hungary. Financial support increasingly takes the form of loans, and is thus accessible only to creditworthy households, in a structure where the state is, in essence, subsidizing the banks through covering interest rate payments.

Market-based lending is contracting as it is currently becoming too expensive for households. According to data published by the Magyar Nemzeti Bank, the central bank of Hungary, there has been a steady decline in new household lending since May 2022 (MNB 2023, Chart 26), with a mildly turning tendency at the end of 2023. This decline is mainly due to a radical drop in the volume of new housing loans, while the volume of new consumer loans declined to a much lesser extent. As a result, the volume of new consumer loans is higher than the volume of new housing loans since July 2022 (MNB 2023, Chart 26). This could be an indication of the varied effects of the current economic crisis: in parallel to the housing market coming to a halt, many households experience difficulties of meeting living costs, or want to implement renovations because of the energy crisis. For both situations, a consumer loan can be the option households have.

With increasing difficulties to purchase housing, the rental market has come under more pressure since 2022. As a result, rental prices have drastically increased, on a national average by 23% in 2022, and 13% in 2023 (MNB 2023, p. 21). This also meant that Hungary, and especially Budapest was one of the least affordable rental markets in Europe, when comparing rental prices to average income levels (*ibid*, p. 22).

Another phenomenon of this new phase of housing financialisation is the increasing share of foreign buyers. In Hungary, their share increased by over 30% from 2021 to 2022 (Futó 2023). They represented 6% of all housing transactions on a national level at the end of 2023, but in popular districts of Budapest more than 20% (MNB 2023, p. 19). This was partially

connected to the devaluation of the Forint, which made Hungarian housing markets more affordable to European investors. Furthermore, since the number of Hungarian households able to purchase housing decreased during this period, the comparative share of foreign buyers was higher.

In Budapest, there is a constantly high share of investor-buyers, steadily representing about 40-50% of all housing transactions in the past years, with the share of investor-buyers also increasing in secondary cities (MNB 2023, p. 9). This means that the myth of purchasing housing for personal housing purposes, and the idea of the homeowner-resident is already not the reality in the capital of Hungary, and by now also not in secondary cities. Nevertheless, the political discourse and regulatory as well as subsidy system is entirely geared towards this myth, while investment-purpose purchases or private rental agreements are barely regulated in any way.

The duration and the outcome of the currently unfolding crisis is yet to be seen, but 2022 and 2023 have definitely represented a halt in the previous, credit-based, expansionary tendency on the Hungarian housing market. Small signs of a return of lending can be seen in early 2024, but with interest rates still high, new lending is still very restricted. However, new forms of housing financialisation are unfolding.

In sum, the current situation exposes the fragile nature of the system of “national” financialisation set up since 2015. Most subsidised loans have been significantly cut, and their overall volume, and even their share in total lending is decreasing (MNB 2023, p. 23). This shows that they are actually not designed in a way to resist market shocks, or to balance housing finance systems out in crisis periods. Thus, apart from being extremely costly for the public budget, these financial mechanisms are not even efficient in securing streams of housing finance, since they act in symbiosis with and serve the interests of market mechanisms. In spite of the postponing measures introduced by the government since 2020, it is apparent that a shift is happening in the housing finance landscape, and that the system in place between 2015 and 2022 will not be able to continue in the same way. Elements that we can currently see do not point towards a less financialised housing market, but surely one that will show different faces of financialisation than previously.

Consequences of shifting regimes of housing financialisation

Tying our empirical findings to the conceptual framework outlined in the beginning of the paper, we have identified three issues which we see as consequences of the above-described shifting regimes of housing financialisation. The three dimensions we discuss in the following

sections shed light on the social and spatial inequalities underpinning the dependent form of housing financialisation which is characteristic of Hungary.

1) Using housing financialisation to strengthen the economic basis of the governing party

Locally variegated forms of financialisation can be understood as the result of the strategies of local elites and of the state to optimize the dependent position they are in through channelling finance and exploiting labour through debt (Reis and Antunas de Oliveira 2021). The class interests of domestic elites will determine how international financial subordination is mediated by the state; how it sets the frameworks and the rules (Alami et al 2022). This is because the locally specific forms of financialisation largely reflect the state's efforts to navigate relations of international financial subordination in a way that is most beneficial to social groups that underpin its power locally. Thus, the state can be understood as an intermediary between global economic processes and local social relations and class interests (Gerócs 2021).

Translating this to the specific case of housing financialisation in Hungary, and specifically to the synergetic system of housing financialisation in place between 2015 and 2022, we can clearly track these class dimensions. Domestic elites and middle classes benefited in various ways from this system. A politically loyal middle class was financially strengthened through subsidies for homeownership, which reinforced the electoral base of the governing party. Domestically owned real estate companies (especially those in oligopolistic positions) benefited from preferential corporate loans, from the boom in the construction sector, and from the demand side subsidies provided to their end-user customers. Financial institutions which were transferred to domestic and public ownership (through preferential lines of financing) during the reconciliation phase after the 2008 crisis benefited from a new boom of lending, which was supported not only by central bank policies of low interest rates, but also by a variety of subsidised household loans. The domestically owned banks were the dominant ones in issuing the various subsidised loans, even though all banks participated in these schemes to some extent.

Thus, evidence suggests that strengthening authoritarianism has actually gone together with deepening financialisation in Hungary; in which the financialisation of housing played an important role.

In order to better understand how the positioning of certain economic elites happens through housing financialisation, it can be worthwhile to specifically scrutinise the sector of real estate development and construction, since this has become a strong economic basis for

the ruling party in Hungary in the past years. With the state subsidies and subsidised loans in place, a lot of money had been poured in on the demand side of the housing market, but since there are serious limitations on the supply side (e.g. in construction materials), the state subsidies have practically been channelled towards the construction / real estate development companies on the housing market (Pósfai et al 2022). The above factors also contributed to the extreme price hikes in housing prices, and to a relatively more profitable residential real estate business.

2) Increasing social inequalities through housing finance

During the period between 2015 and 2022, there was a dualization in the field of lending to households (Pósfai 2018, Jelinek and Pósfai 2019). While higher income households could benefit from safer and better regulated mortgage loans (thanks to various debt brake regulations introduced after the 2008 crisis), lower income people were taking higher and higher volumes of more risky forms of debt (consumer loans, personal loans, credit overdraft). This is similar to the tendency that can be observed in other Central and Eastern European countries (Gagyí and Mikus, 2022).

Non-mortgaged forms of loans have grown faster than mortgage debt, and according to central bank statistics, are much more prevalent among lower-income groups. While 60% of all mortgage loans were taken by the highest-income quintile in 2021, over 30% of personal loans issued by non-bank financial actors were taken by the lowest-income quintile (MNB 2022b, p.30). This highlights two important tendencies. The first is that mortgage loans are indeed the privilege of higher-income households. The poor do not feature as customers of mortgage loans (mortgage loan issuance in the lower two income quintiles is entirely negligible), but their debt dependence is nevertheless growing. The second issue to highlight is the importance of non-bank financial institutions in lending to lower-income households. These financial institutions are subject to very little research, and the focus on international banking groups – which are, essentially, the dominant financial institutions in the CEE region – has overlooked the class dimension of whom these different types of institutions provide services to (Mikus and Rodik, 2021b).

These characteristics of the indebtedness of lower-income households are important from the perspective of housing financialisation because often these loans are also used for housing purposes. Furthermore, they demonstrate that the debt-based strategies of the government can increase the social gap between those households who are able to use debt as a leverage for wealth creation, and those who become involved in more risky forms of debt.

The fact that the housing subsidies in place between 2015 and 2023 gave higher levels of financial support for newly built units also meant that households with more savings and higher income – that is, with a higher downpayment potential and able to take a larger loan – are the ones that could benefit the most from the system. Furthermore, these subsidies were all tied to long-term employment (or self-employment), and the debtor also needed to qualify for the regular loan-testing criteria of the banks (which can be stricter than the legal minimum). Thus, middle-class families with stable and regularized income were most able to benefit from them. Banks which provide these subsidies and subsidised loans have confirmed in previous research (Pósfai et al 2022) that there are some social groups who are systematically being missed by these instruments. Furthermore, there are others, who slipped out of the bankable category between 2020 and 2023 due to the deteriorating economic environment in Hungary.

Housing subsidies in Hungary are systematically introduced in a pro-cyclical way, spending more public money in periods of conjuncture – thus also further fuelling asset price bubbles on the housing market. This means that housing becomes more expensive for everyone, but the beneficiaries of the subsidies represent a much narrower social group. At the same time, there are no non-profit or anti-commodifying housing interventions. As a result, housing inequalities increase during these periods of housing market upswing.

As a consequence of the latest crisis tendencies, the share of investor-buyers increased during 2022. This is also because during this year, interest rates were at record high levels, thus potential buyers who needed a mortgage preferred to postpone their housing purchase. Investor-buyers were the ones able to buy without a mortgage. As the possibilities for buying housing narrowed, more households appeared on the rental market. This increased pressure, together with the lack of rental regulation, resulted in quickly increasing rental prices from mid-2022 onwards (MNB 2023). This pattern means that on the one hand the rental income of investor-buyers increased, and on the other hand the financial burden on renting households also increased – thus amplifying inequalities between those who own and those who rent.

3) Increasing spatial inequalities on the housing market: a strengthening urban-rural divide

As previously argued, dependent integration in international financial relations results in more volatile cycles on the housing market in Hungary (Bródy and Pósfai 2020). This volatility also has marked spatial consequences. In expansive periods of housing finance – during cycles when finance is abundant – spatial inequalities increase, and specific localities experience dramatic house price increases and an increase in the pace and number of transactions (Pósfai

2018). However, it is inherent to the dependent / financially subordinate position of the country that in crisis periods these financial flows abruptly stop, and many aspects of the housing market (mainly the speed and number of transactions) begin to stagnate or to decline. Thus, between 2008 and 2015 stagnation was the main characteristic of the Hungarian housing market, which meant that spatial inequalities decreased somewhat. Nevertheless, spatial mobility was not made easier for households, since this stagnation was always more characteristic of rural housing markets than core urban ones, making mobility to urban centres (with more employment) difficult in the context of a housing market dominated so much by individual ownership.

Then, between 2015 and 2022 there was an unprecedented increase in new lending volumes and in house prices. During this period, spatial inequalities and thus the polarization of the housing market increased, with preferential localities of the housing market experiencing the boom to the highest extent. These preferential spaces were somewhat varied: for investment purposes they meant mainly the inner districts of the capital city of Budapest, while for beneficiaries of state housing subsidies and subsidised loans, they were the external districts of Budapest and other larger cities, as well as towns in the agglomeration areas. This is because these were the locations where new-build projects could be realized, and where – despite the increase in prices – the subsidies could still mean substantial support.

These geographies, especially that of agglomeration areas are blueprints for understanding the spatial consequences of unstable channels of housing finance, because housing market booms and busts systematically affect the same (or similar) types of spaces (Gagyí, Jelinek, Pósfai and Vígvári 2021). The neighbourhoods in agglomeration areas expand in expansive phases of housing finance, but without urban planning being able to follow the pace of developments, thus leading to a lack of services. The more marginal parts of agglomeration areas also become homes to financially more vulnerable households, who risk ending up in financial difficulties or loan default during a crisis (ibid). The second half of 2022 again brought a dramatic fall – mainly in new housing loans and housing transactions numbers. We are yet to see the socio-spatial consequences of the current contraction of housing finance.

The state intervenes in these spatial processes in various ways. First of all, the way in which the housing subsidies and subsidised loans are designed pushes money towards specific segments of the housing market. Another important characteristic of the subsidies was that they pushed different actors towards the segment of newly constructed housing (while neglecting renovation) both on the demand side (higher subsidies for new-build) and on the supply side (preferential VAT). Furthermore, in the case of some large real estate development

projects, it has become a practice to give preferential regulatory frames, which allow the developer to act outside of the local zoning regulations of the given municipality. This makes it possible for real estate developers enjoying these benefits to construct in localities (especially within Budapest), where this would not be possible, or would not be profitable for other companies.

There have been several calls to take space more seriously in processes of international financial subordination (Sokol 2017, Alami et al 2022), but this aspect is nevertheless seldom integrated. Especially not with a multi-scalar understanding, that would explain how local spatial inequalities (including those at the urban level) are constituent to broader international dependencies (Hürtgen 2015, Gagyí, Jelinek, Pósfai and Vigvári 2021). Thus, the currently unfolding crisis will be especially interesting to scrutinize.

Conclusions and looking forward

In our paper, we analysed how housing financialisation in Hungary connects to broader economic processes, what the underlying political rationales are, as well as what class structure it builds on. We argued that different distinct measures connected to housing financialisation can be seen systematically, and that they are connected to broader dependent relations under capitalist cycles. The interest of scrutinizing the rather specific case of housing financialisation in Hungary lies in the fact that it “tells a story” about one of the tools that the elite of a small country, in a globally dependent position can apply in its quest to stabilise its internal political power and its underlying economic base. This comes at the price of increasing internal inequalities, and an increasingly financialised housing market.

We want to draw attention to the conundrum of what will come after the current turning point in housing financialisation, introduced by the economic turmoil of 2022-2023. The current economic environment, with the end of the period of historically low interest rates, and an increasing pool of households who cannot access conventional mortgages, the question is very urgent: what new forms of housing finance can emerge, and can these facilitate more accessible and affordable forms of housing? Will we merely experience a period of very reduced housing market activity, and then – pushed with a new set of state intervention – come back to the business-as-usual of individual mortgage loans? Will investment-based housing finance expand, due to an upcoming period of inaccessibility of the housing market to anyone who does not have sufficient capital upfront, without needing to borrow? Will the current crisis period open the political and economic possibility of new, nonprofit forms of housing finance in Hungary and in the region? It is too early to say.

What is clear, however, is that in Hungary, and elsewhere in Central and Eastern Europe, the crisis highlights the need to consider new forms of housing tenure. As long as these countries remain locked in super-homeownership structures, housing financialisation through individual household debt will prevail, reproducing the same controversies outlined throughout this article. There is a dire need for new forms of tenure (rental and cooperative), and for a response to the housing crisis which escalated in countries of the region in the past decade. This means that new organizations of housing provision need to emerge, which, in turn, need new forms of housing finance (Pósfai et al 2022). In the absence of these new forms, we are most likely merely facing a new period of housing financialisation which will benefit a new round of beneficiaries, but will not change the fundamental structure of accumulation through the housing market or disrupt “financial chains” on which this structure rests.

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